

Comparative Evaluation of Antimicrobial Efficacy of Triple Antibiotic Paste, Calcium Hydroxide, And Tulsi + Moringa Leaf Extract Against *Enterococcus Faecalis*: An In-Vitro Study

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ABSTRACT

The present study aims to evaluate and compare the antimicrobial efficacy of Triple antibiotic paste (TAP), Calcium hydroxide, and a combination of Tulsi and Moringa extract against *Enterococcus faecalis*. A total of 21 agar plate specimens were divided into three groups (n = 7): Group A - Calcium hydroxide, Group B - TAP, and Group C - Tulsi + Moringa extract. Antimicrobial efficacy was assessed using the agar well diffusion method. Zones of inhibition were measured after incubation at 37°C for 24 hours. The mean zone of inhibition was highest in the TAP group (32.43 ± 2.88 mm), followed by the herbal extract group (21.57 ± 1.81 mm), and lowest in the calcium hydroxide group (10.71 ± 1.49 mm). The difference was statistically highly significant (p < 0.001). TAP showed superior antimicrobial efficacy followed by the Tulsi + Moringa combination, with promising antibacterial activity and may serve as an alternative intracanal medicament.

Keywords: Calcium hydroxide; *Enterococcus faecalis*; Moringa; Triple antibiotic paste; Tulsi.

INTRODUCTION

Successful endodontic treatment primarily depends on effective disinfection of the root canal system.¹ Microorganisms play a crucial role in the etiology of pulpal and periapical diseases, with *Enterococcus faecalis* being one of the most frequently associated pathogens in persistent endodontic infections.² Its ability to survive in harsh environmental conditions, penetrate dentinal tubules, and form biofilms contributes to its resistance to conventional treatment modalities.³ Calcium hydroxide has long been considered the gold standard intracanal medicament due to its high pH and antibacterial properties.⁴ However, *E. faecalis* has demonstrated resistance to calcium hydroxide, limiting its effectiveness.⁵ Triple antibiotic paste (TAP), consisting of ciprofloxacin, metronidazole, and minocycline, has been widely used due to its broad-spectrum antimicrobial activity.⁶

Despite its effectiveness, it is associated with drawbacks such as tooth discoloration and cytotoxicity.⁷ Recently, there has been increasing interest in herbal medicaments due to their biocompatibility and antimicrobial properties.⁸ The antimicrobial effect of Tulsi (*Ocimum sanctum*) has been attributed to bioactive compounds such as eugenol, ursolic acid, carvacrol, and linalool. Moringa (*Moringa oleifera*) Moringa contains a wide range of biologically active constituents, including flavonoids, tannins, alkaloids, phenolic compounds, saponins, and isothiocyanates, all of which contribute to its antimicrobial activity.⁹ However, their combined use as an intracanal medicament remains underexplored. Hence, the aim of the present study was to compare the antimicrobial efficacy of Tulsi + Moringa extract with TAP and calcium hydroxide against *Enterococcus faecalis*

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MATERIALS AND METHOD

Enterococcus faecalis (ATCC 29212) was used as the test microorganism. The organism was cultured on blood agar plates and incubated at 37°C for 24 hours to obtain discrete colonies. A well-isolated colony was then inoculated into 5 mL of brain–heart infusion (BHI) broth and incubated at 37°C for 24 hours. The bacterial growth was confirmed by the presence of turbidity in the broth. The turbidity of the bacterial suspension was then adjusted to match the 0.5 McFarland standard, corresponding to approximately 1.5×10^8 CFU/mL, to ensure uniformity of the inoculum. This standardized bacterial suspension was used for subsequent antimicrobial testing. The antimicrobial efficacy of the intracanal medicaments was evaluated using the agar well diffusion method. A total of 21 samples were divided into three groups (n = 7 per group):

- **Group A:** Calcium hydroxide
- **Group B:** Triple antibiotic paste (TAP)
- **Group C:** Tulsi (*Ocimum sanctum*) + Moringa (*Moringa oleifera*) extract

Calcium hydroxide (Prime, India) was obtained in powder form and mixed with sterile saline on a glass slab using a sterile spatula to obtain a homogeneous paste of suitable consistency. Triple antibiotic paste was prepared by mixing ciprofloxacin, metronidazole, and minocycline in a 1:1:1 ratio using sterile techniques to achieve a uniform paste. For preparation of the herbal extract, fresh leaves of Tulsi (*Ocimum sanctum*) and Moringa (*Moringa oleifera*) were collected from a pesticide-free source. The leaves were thoroughly washed under running water and air-

dried at room temperature. The dried leaves were ground separately into fine powders using an electric grinder and sieved to obtain uniform particle size. Equal quantities (10 g each) of Tulsi and Moringa powders were mixed and added to 200 mL of sterile distilled water. The mixture was heated in a water bath at 60–70°C for 30 minutes, followed by cooling to room temperature. The resultant extract was used for antimicrobial testing.

Figure 1 – Tulsi + Moringa Extract

Antimicrobial Activity Assay

Sterile agar plates were inoculated with *E. faecalis* using a sterile swab to ensure uniform distribution of the microorganism over the agar surface. Wells of 6 mm diameter were prepared in the agar using a sterile borer. Each well was filled with the respective medicament under aseptic conditions. All procedures were carried out under laminar airflow to prevent contamination. The inoculated plates were incubated at 37°C for 24 hours. After incubation, the antimicrobial activity was assessed by measuring the zones of inhibition around each well using a digital caliper, and the values were recorded in millimeters.

Fig 2 – Zone of inhibition of medicaments (A - Calcium hydroxide, B -TAP , C- Tulsi+ Moringa extract)

Statistical Analysis

The mean and standard deviation (SD) of the zone of inhibition (mm) were calculated for all groups. Intergroup comparison was performed using one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA), followed by Tukey's post hoc test for pairwise comparisons. A p-value < 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

RESULTS

One-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) revealed a highly significant difference among the three groups ($F = 179.25$, $p < 0.001$), indicating a significant variation in antimicrobial efficacy among the tested medicaments.

The mean zone of inhibition was highest in the TAP group (32.43 ± 2.88 mm), followed by the herbal extract group (21.57 ± 1.81 mm), and lowest in the calcium hydroxide group (10.71 ± 1.49 mm).

Fig 3 – Comparison of antimicrobial efficacy of medicaments

Table 1 – Mean zone of inhibition of the medicaments

Groups	N	Mean (mm)	Std. Deviation
Calcium Hydroxide	7	10.71	1.49
TAP	7	32.43	2.88
Herbal Extract	7	21.57	1.81
Total	21	21.57	9.24

DISCUSSION

Successful endodontic treatment depends largely on the effective elimination of microorganisms from the root canal system.¹ However, complete disinfection remains difficult because of the complex anatomy of the root canal space, including lateral canals, fins, isthmuses, and dentinal tubules, which provide favorable niches for microbial survival.¹¹ Although

chemomechanical preparation significantly reduces the microbial load, residual microorganisms may persist within inaccessible areas of the canal system, necessitating the use of intracanal medicaments.¹² The present study compared the antimicrobial efficacy of calcium hydroxide, triple antibiotic paste (TAP), and a combination of Tulsi (*Ocimum sanctum*) and Moringa (*Moringa oleifera*) extracts against

Enterococcus faecalis, a microorganism frequently implicated in persistent endodontic infections and post-treatment disease. The findings of the present study demonstrated that TAP exhibited the highest antimicrobial activity against *E. faecalis*, followed by the Tulsi–Moringa combination, while calcium hydroxide showed the least antibacterial efficacy. These results suggest that although conventional intracanal medicaments remain useful, alternative herbal formulations may offer promising antimicrobial effects and warrant further investigation. The superior antimicrobial activity observed with TAP can be attributed to the synergistic action of its constituent antibiotics—metronidazole, ciprofloxacin, and minocycline.⁶ Hoshino et al. first proposed the concept of combining antibiotics to eliminate the diverse microbial flora present within infected root canals.¹³ Metronidazole is highly effective against obligate anaerobes, ciprofloxacin targets Gram-negative bacteria, and minocycline exhibits broad-spectrum activity against both Gram-positive and Gram-negative microorganisms. The combined action of these agents results in a wide antimicrobial spectrum capable of eliminating resistant bacterial species, including *E. faecalis*.⁷ Previous investigations by Windley et al. and Sato et al. similarly reported substantial antibacterial activity of TAP against endodontic pathogens, supporting the findings of the present study.^{14,15} The effectiveness of TAP against *E. faecalis* is particularly important because this microorganism possesses several virulence factors that contribute to its persistence within treated root canals. These include the ability to penetrate deep into dentinal tubules, adherence to collagen-rich dentin, tolerance to nutritional deprivation, and survival under harsh environmental conditions. Furthermore, *E. faecalis* can form highly organized biofilms that enhance bacterial resistance to antimicrobial agents and host defense mechanisms. The broad-spectrum nature of TAP enables it to overcome many of these resistance mechanisms, resulting in superior antibacterial efficacy.⁷ The herbal combination of Tulsi and Moringa demonstrated moderate antibacterial activity, which was significantly greater than that of calcium hydroxide. The antimicrobial effect of Tulsi has been attributed to bioactive compounds such as eugenol, ursolic acid, carvacrol, and linalool. These phytochemicals disrupt bacterial cell membranes,

interfere with enzyme systems, and inhibit microbial growth. In addition to its antibacterial action, Tulsi possesses anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, and immunomodulatory properties that may be beneficial in regenerative and minimally invasive endodontic procedures.⁸ Similarly, Moringa contains a wide range of biologically active constituents, including flavonoids, tannins, alkaloids, phenolic compounds, saponins, and isothiocyanates, all of which contribute to its antimicrobial activity. These compounds have been reported to inhibit bacterial proliferation by altering membrane permeability, disrupting cellular metabolism, and inducing oxidative damage to microbial cells.⁹ The combination of Tulsi and Moringa may therefore produce a synergistic antimicrobial effect through multiple mechanisms of action. The present findings are consistent with previous studies that have demonstrated the antibacterial potential of herbal extracts against oral and endodontic pathogens. The growing interest in herbal intracanal medicaments is driven by concerns regarding the disadvantages associated with antibiotic-based formulations. Although TAP exhibits excellent antimicrobial efficacy, prolonged use may contribute to bacterial resistance, tooth discoloration due to minocycline, allergic reactions, and potential cytotoxic effects on stem cells at higher concentrations.⁷ Herbal alternatives, in contrast, are generally biocompatible, readily available, economical, and associated with fewer adverse effects. Therefore, the moderate antibacterial activity demonstrated by the Tulsi–Moringa combination in the present study suggests its potential as a natural intracanal medicament, particularly in situations where long-term biocompatibility is a primary concern.⁸ Calcium hydroxide exhibited the lowest antibacterial efficacy among the tested groups. This finding is in agreement with several previous investigations that have reported limited effectiveness of calcium hydroxide against *E. faecalis*. The antibacterial action of calcium hydroxide is primarily attributed to the release of hydroxyl ions, which increase the environmental pH and disrupt bacterial cellular structures.⁴ However, *E. faecalis* possesses adaptive mechanisms that enable it to tolerate alkaline conditions. Evans et al. demonstrated that *E. faecalis* can survive in environments with elevated pH through proton pump mechanisms that help maintain intracellular homeostasis. Furthermore, the buffering

capacity of dentin reduces the alkalinity achieved within dentinal tubules, thereby limiting the antimicrobial effectiveness of calcium hydroxide in clinical situations.⁵ Haapasalo and Ørstavik reported that *E. faecalis* located within dentinal tubules could survive exposure to calcium hydroxide for prolonged periods, highlighting the inability of this medicament to completely eliminate resistant microorganisms.¹⁶ The organism's capacity to form biofilms further reduces susceptibility to calcium hydroxide by restricting penetration of hydroxyl ions into deeper bacterial layers.¹⁷ Consequently, although calcium hydroxide remains widely used because of its tissue-dissolving capability, anti-inflammatory effects, and ability to induce hard tissue formation, its antimicrobial activity against persistent endodontic pathogens appears limited. The present study has certain limitations. Being an in vitro investigation, the experimental conditions may not fully replicate the complexity of the clinical environment, where factors such as tissue remnants, dentin buffering, host immune responses, and multispecies biofilms influence antimicrobial effectiveness. In addition, only a single bacterial species was evaluated. Future studies should investigate the efficacy of these medicaments against polymicrobial biofilms and assess their cytotoxicity, biocompatibility, substantivity, and clinical performance through in vivo and randomized clinical studies. Within the limitations of this study, TAP demonstrated the highest antimicrobial efficacy against *E. faecalis*, followed by the Tulsi–Moringa combination and calcium hydroxide. The findings suggest that the herbal combination possesses promising antibacterial properties and may serve as a potential natural alternative intracanal medicament. Further investigations are required to validate its clinical applicability and establish its long-term effectiveness in endodontic therapy.

CONCLUSION

This in vitro study concluded that, triple antibiotic paste demonstrated the highest antimicrobial efficacy against *Enterococcus faecalis*, followed by the Tulsi (*Ocimum sanctum*) and Moringa (*Moringa oleifera*) combination, while calcium hydroxide showed the least effectiveness. The herbal formulation exhibited significant antibacterial activity, suggesting its

potential as a biocompatible alternative intracanal medicament. However, further in vivo studies and clinical trials are necessary to validate its efficacy and applicability in clinical practice.

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